

ENHANCING STUDENTS' CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING IN GENERAL BIOLOGY 2 THROUGH FLIPPED INQUIRY-BASED LEARNING (FIBL)

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ABSTRACT

This study utilized a one group pretest-post research design to investigate the level of conceptual understanding of students exposed to Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning (FIBL) in General Biology 2. A self-made Conceptual Understanding Test (CUT) questionnaire, validated by experts, was utilized to gather data from the students of Grade 12 Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) program selected through purposive sampling. The study employed descriptive statistics along with a paired t-test. The findings revealed that the proficiency level of the students' conceptual understanding did not reach the desired level in the pretest and it transitioned to fairly satisfactory in the posttest which was also maintained in the retention test. Furthermore, the mean scores of the students before and after the FIBL intervention is found to be significantly different. Likewise, a significant difference is also evident in the mean scores of students between the posttest and retention test. This suggests that the implementation of Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning was successful in improving the students' conceptual understanding. This study recommends that educators may use FIBL as an approach to improve the conceptual understanding of the students. Educational institutions may also offer training workshops for teachers on its best practices and further research on its effectiveness may also be conducted.

Keywords: *conceptual understanding, flipped inquiry-based learning*

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-changing educational landscape, the need for effective and innovative teaching strategies and methods is of great importance. In science teaching for instance, it does not only involve putting the abstract and theoretical scientific concepts into action through experimentation but it also involves students to create meaningful connections between one scientific concept to another. Having an organized web of ideas allows students to relate their understanding of concepts to different contexts. In biology, for instance, students are presented with a wide range of biological concepts that may be hard to conceptualize, especially because most of these processes are not visible to the naked eye. With a well-constructed facts and concepts web, students can best relate what they learned with their experiences. Moreover, teachers nowadays frequently engage their students with active learning activities paired with inquiry-based activities in order to improve their conceptual understanding (Aidoo et al., 2022).

However, most students are still rooted in memorizing biological facts or that students find biology difficult due to their inability to imagine abstract concepts. These factors were seen as the drivers of the declining level of the conceptual understanding of students by which it was revealed that they fail to make a meaningful relationship of the ideas that they've learned (Wardyaningrum & Suyanto, 2019). Even if the teachers choose to involve students in direct discovery through experimentation, our country, the Philippines, still faces the challenges of inadequate laboratory resources mainly for conducting these laboratory activities (Duban et al., 2019). In fact, in the recently released result of the assessment of Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) conducted last year, 2022, which includes Science as one of the subjects, it was reported that Filipino students had a low performance, with the Philippines ranked 73 out of 74 participating countries (Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe, 2023). In line with this, the low conceptual understanding of students in their general biology subject has become one of the concerns for biology teachers in Central Mindanao Laboratory High School. This is in accordance with the interview conducted with the cooperating teachers of the pre-service teachers in the said school as well as from the observations of pre-service teachers during their Field Study 1- Observation of Teaching-Learning in Actual School Environment.

On the other hand, an efficient method to enhance active-learning strategies in the classroom while offering personalized support to students is by “flipping” the classroom (Jacques & Lequeu, 2020). Flipped classroom is a teaching method where the course materials are provided. These materials are usually video-based lectures which enable students to engage outside the classroom while in-class is used for working together on projects and learning activities (Hamdan et al., 2013). Furthermore, in order to make this method more effective, approaches can be improved by merging it with another teaching method such as inquiry-based learning (IBL) (Schallert et al., 2021). According to Heindl (2018), IBL involves a range of student-centered approaches, allowing the students to take responsibility for their learning and build knowledge through interactions and encourages the application of knowledge to address real-world challenges. Through the implementation of the Flipped-Inquiry-Based Learning (FIBL), teachers can plan out

arrangements for their activities both within and outside of the class schedule and students engage in both independent and collaborative learning with their peers which help them improve in the learning process (Asiksoy & Ozdamli, 2017).

With the new approaches to learning, flipped inquiry-based learning may help increase students' conceptual understanding in General Biology 2. Hence, it is hoped that assessing the proficiency level of the students' conceptual understanding using flipped inquiry-based learning would provide useful learning that would allow them to enhance their performance in science and can provide appropriate strategies and techniques for teachers that can improve the teaching-learning process.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this action research is to assess the effectiveness of the Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning in improving students' conceptual understanding in General Biology 2. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the students' proficiency level of their conceptual understanding in General Biology 2 before and after being exposed to Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning (FIBL) in relation to:
 - a. pre-test;
 - b. post-test; and
 - c. retention test?
2. Is there a significant difference between the students' mean scores before and after the intervention?
3. Is there a significant difference between the students' mean scores in post test and retention tes

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The intervention of this study was conducted to the Grade 12 - Academic Track: Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) learners of Central Mindanao University Laboratory which is under the College of Education, one of the colleges of Central Mindanao University - a Teacher Education Institution. The school is located in University Town, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon.

Sampling Method

A purposive sampling was utilized in identifying the participants of this study. These are the 33 students of Grade 12 - Galileo which has 19 males and 14 females of Central Mindanao University Laboratory High School. The researchers believed that the Grade-12 Galileo students are best fitted to be this study's respondents as they are taking General Biology 2 that mostly need a high level of conceptual understanding.

Research Instrument

The researchers in the study used a self-made Conceptual Understanding Test (CUT) questionnaire to assess the level of students' conceptual understanding in General Biology 2, specifically focusing on the topic of *Evolution and Origin of Biodiversity*. The questionnaire had thirty (30) items multiple-choice questions. As can be gleaned, Table 1 shows the test-blueprint of the questionnaire.

Table 1. Test Blueprint of 30-item multiple choice Conceptual Understanding Test in General Biology 2

Topic	Weight	Remembering (13%)	Understanding (17%)	Applying (10%)	Analyzing (33%)	Evaluating (27%)	Total
Biodiversity	30%	2	1	1	3	2	9
Evolution	30%	1	2	1	3	2	9
Evidence of Evolution	20%		1	1	2	2	6
Mechanisms of Evolution	20%	1	1		2	2	6
Total	100%	4	5	3	10	8	30

The questionnaire was validated by three Science Education experts. These experts reviewed the content of the questionnaire, the construction of the stem and choices, and the alignment of the questions with the learning competencies of the General

Biology 2 curriculum and if the questions fit on the corresponding Bloom's cognitive domain. Furthermore, the reliability of the questionnaire was assessed through a pilot testing with forty (40) freshmen in the Science Education students from Central Mindanao University - College of Education. The internal consistency or reliability of the questionnaire was determined using Cronbach's alpha, which measured the consistency of responses across the items. The Cronbach's alpha value of the questionnaire was 0.733 with a descriptive interpretation of reliable and acceptable.

The following grading percentile, interpretation and remarks adopted from DepEd Order No. 8s. 2015 was used to interpret students' scores in the pretest, posttest and retention test of undergoing the flipped inquiry-based learning.

Score Range	Grading Percentile	Level of Proficiency
28-30	90-100	Outstanding
25-27	85-89	Very Satisfactory
22-24	80-84	Satisfactory
18-21	75-79	Fairly Satisfactory
0-17	74 below	Did Not Meet Expectations

Data Gathering Procedure

The data was collected using a 30-item self-made Conceptual Understanding Test (CUT). In proving the validity and the reliability of the questionnaire, the researchers requested three (3) biology teaching experts and administered a pilot testing to forty (40) first year science education students. The internal consistency reliability of the questionnaires were found acceptable with Cronbach's alpha, $\alpha=0.733$. The researchers asked permission to conduct the action research to the Dean of the College of Education Dean, Dr. Denis A. Tan and the Principal of CMU-Laboratory High School, Dr. Joemar B. Capuyan. Following the approval, a consent form was given to the respondents as a proof of their voluntary participation. Then, the students of Grade-12 Galileo answered the pre-test. The researchers also oriented the respondents about the details of the intervention. This orientation covered information on the researchers, research title, study purpose, time commitment, the overview of the questionnaire, potential risks and benefits of participation, the confidentiality of the data gathered, and flipped inquiry-based learning. Also, the researchers emphasized that there is a posttest and retention test after the treatment or intervention has been administered to the participants. Generally, the quantitative data was collected through the pretest, posttest, and retention test. The intervention started from the 1st of April until the 6th of May, 2024.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive statistics was used in analyzing the data obtained, specifically it includes mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentage. Paired t test is a

statistical tool that compares the means of two measurements of the same group taken from different times. This best suits in scrutinizing data gathered from a one-group pretest-posttest research design where the mean scores from the pretest of the students was compared on the posttest mean results after the intervention has been administered. In this study, the mean scores of the pretest of the grade twelve students was tested to assess the difference towards their post test such that flipped inquiry-based learning has been introduced in the said treatment group. If the result of paired t test is zero, therefore there is no difference on the mean scores and thus the intervention is not effective.

Scope and Delimitation

The intent of this study is to to determine the students' proficiency level of their conceptual understanding in General Biology 2 before and after being exposed to Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning and to identify whether there is a significant difference between the mean scores before and after the intervention as well as the post test and retention test. The participants were chosen through a purposive sampling where 33 students in Grade 12 - Galileo from Central Mindanao University Laboratory High School as they have General Biology 2 subject in the semester.

Moreover, the study utilized a crafted, validated, and pilot tested 30-item multiple choice questionnaire to measure the conceptual understanding of the students. The intervention of the study followed Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning thus the dissemination of lesson is through using online learning management system and in-class inquiry session.

One group pretest and posttest was used as the research design to emphasize the effectiveness of Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning to the conceptual understanding of students in General Biology 2 for the second semester of academic year 2023-2024.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of data from the students' scores relevant to testing the research hypotheses. Tables were presented in this section to provide an easier analysis of the data. The order of the presentation follows the arrangement of the problems identified in the study.

Proficiency Level of Students' Conceptual Understanding in General Biology 2

Table 2. Proficiency level of students' conceptual understanding in General Biology 2

Level of Proficiency	Score Range	Grading Percentile	Pre-test		Post-test		Retention Test	
			N	%	N	%	N	%
Outstanding	28-30	90-100	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Satisfactory	25-27	85-89	0	0	0	0	4	12
Satisfactory	22-24	80-84	1	3	6	18	14	42
Fairly Satisfactory	18-21	75-79	10	30	14	42	11	33
Did Not Meet Expectations	0-17	Below 75	22	67	13	39	4	12
TOTAL			33	100	33	100	33	100
Mean ± SD			15.8 ± 3.9		18.8 ± 2.8		21.3 ± 2.8	
CUT Proficiency Level			Did Not Meet Expectations		Fairly Satisfactory		Fairly Satisfactory	

Table 2 presents the results of students' Conceptual Understanding Test (CUT) in General Biology 2 in relation to pretest, post test and retention test. The pretest results revealed a mean score of 15.8 with a standard deviation of 3.9, indicating that the proficiency level of Grade 12-STEM Galileo “Did Not Meet Expectations”. This implies that most of the students have a low conceptual understanding of the subject matter. This is expected because they may lack prior knowledge on the topic of *Evolution and Origin of Biodiversity*. This result aligns with the study of Zubaidah, et. al. (2018), who found out that factors such as the lack of prior knowledge can influence students' performance during the initial assessments.

Furthermore, a notable improvement was observed during the post test. The post-test obtained a mean score of 18.8 with a 2.8 standard deviation, indicating that the student's proficiency level improved to “Fairly Satisfactory”. This result reflects the positive impact of Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning (FIBL) on the conceptual understanding of students in General Biology 2. Further, the results highlight the importance of leveraging technology to promote active participation and independent learning among students to improve their conceptual understanding (Aidoo et al., 2022; Asiksoy & Ozdamli, 2017; & Tan et. al, 2020). While the positive impact is evident, it is also worth noting that thirteen (13) or 39% of the students did not meet expectations. To support the needs of these students, targeted interventions such as individualized remediation sessions and additional support resources may be implemented to address their learning gaps and

improve their conceptual understanding proficiency level of the subject matter (Tan et al., 2020).

On the other hand, the retention test of the CUT has a mean score of 21.3 with a standard deviation of 2.8, indicating a “Fairly Satisfactory” proficiency level. This result suggests that a significant portion of the students were able to retain and demonstrate their conceptual understanding in General Biology 2. This result conforms to the study of Gasparic (2024) which revealed that the use of this learning technique allows students to remember what they learned better compared to a traditional teaching method. However, it is important to continue improving the learning experience for all students, especially those who did not meet expectations.

Students’ Mean Scores Before and After FIBL

Table 3 presents the t-test value of means derived from the results of the students’ pretest and post test in measuring their conceptual understanding in General Biology 2.

Table 3. t-Test value of Means in Pretest and Post-test of Students’ Conceptual Understanding in General Biology 2

	Paired Difference			95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Lower	Upper			
Pre-test- Post-test	-2.97	0.425	0.151	-3.12	-2.82	-3.84	32	0.000**

Legend:

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) NS- not significant

As can be gleaned, the results revealed a mean paired difference of -2.97, a standard deviation of 0.425, and a standard error mean of 0.151. Additionally, this is supported by a 95% confidence interval that spans from -3.12 to -2.82. The negative mean paired difference suggests an average increase in scores from the pretest to the post-test. This positive outcome is further supported by the t value of -3.84 and p-value of 0.000 implying an extremely significant difference in mean scores of the pre-test and post-test. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no significant difference in the students’ mean scores before and after being exposed to Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning (FIBL) in General Biology 2” was rejected.

The results imply that the use of FIBL where students need to access the learning materials in advance prior to the face-to-face class helped them perform better as reflected in the increase of the students’ scores during post-test. These findings conform with the research of Hamdan et al. (2022) on the use of inquiry-based learning (IBL) in a

flipped classroom. The researchers highlighted that implementing IBL in a flipped classroom setting resulted in notable differences in students' scores between the pretest and post test assessments. In addition, the use of the said intervention enhances the conceptual knowledge and inquiry skills of the students. In light of this finding, the study of Aidoo et al. (2022) emphasized that the combination of a flipped classroom and inquiry-based learning bears a positive benefit which improves students' performance and even fosters critical thinking skills.

Students' Mean Scores in the Posttest and Retention Test

Table 4 displays the t-test value of means in the students' post-test and retention test.

Table 4. t-Test value of Means in Posttest and Retention-test of Students' Conceptual Understanding in General Biology 2

	Paired Difference			95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Lower	Upper			
Post-test-Retention test	-2.52	0.003	0.001	-2.52	-2.51	2.04	32	0.000**

Legend:

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) NS- not significant

As shown, Table 4 reveals a mean paired difference of -2.52, a standard deviation of 0.003, and a standard error mean of 0.001. This is further supported by a 95% confidence interval ranging from -2.52 to -2.51. This means that there is an average increase in the scores from post-test to retention test, implying that students were able to improve and retain their conceptual understanding in General Biology 2. To reinforce this, conducting a paired t-test for post-test and retention test is crucial as it assesses the long-term retention of knowledge and skills acquired during the implementation of the intervention.

The t value=2.04 and p-value=0.000 results indicate that there is an extremely significant difference in mean scores between the post-test and retention test. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that "there is no significant difference between the mean scores of the students in the posttest and retention test exposed to Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning (FIBL) in General Biology 2" is rejected. This finding implies that students exposed to FIBL were able to recall what they learned during the retention test which was administered two weeks after the posttest.

In light with this, the study of Paristiowati et al. (2017) supports that there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of the students in a flipped inquiry-based classroom. This finding is further supported by Laksana et.al (2019), who specifically examined the effects of flipped inquiry-based learning (FIBL) and found that students demonstrated improved critical thinking skills and a deeper understanding of scientific concepts compared to those in traditional lecture-based settings. This study highlighted that students taught through flipped inquiry-based methods retain information better over time compared to those taught through traditional lecture methods.

Conclusions

The findings of this study led to the following conclusions:

The conceptual understanding proficiency level of Grade 12 STEM Galileo students of Central Mindanao University-Laboratory High School reveals the following: the pretest mean scores “Did Not Meet Expectations”, the post-test scores demonstrated a shift to “Fairly Satisfactory”, and this level was maintained in the retention test.

There is a significant difference in the students’ mean scores before and after being exposed to Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning (FIBL) in General Biology 2. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

There is a significant difference between the mean scores of the students in the posttest and retention test exposed to Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning (FIBL) in General Biology 2. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Recommendations

The results, findings, and conclusions of the study have led to the following recommendations for further research.

The teachers in General Biology 2 may implement flipped inquiry-based learning (FIBL) as this approach has shown a premise in enhancing students’ conceptual understanding. Additionally, this approach can monitor students’ progress effectively, allowing teachers to identify areas where additional support is needed.

Teachers implementing FIBL may offer individualized remediation sessions and additional support resources to address the needs of students who did not meet expectations. These sessions can be tailored to each student's specific areas of difficulty identified through ongoing assessments and formative evaluations.

Educational institutions or external professional development providers specializing in instructional methodologies may offer professional development for educators on best practices in FIBL. These entities can organize workshops, seminars,

or online training sessions to support educators in developing their skills and knowledge in implementing FIBL effectively. Additionally, educators themselves may take the initiative to seek out professional development opportunities, such as attending conferences or enrolling in courses focused on FIBL practices.

Future researchers may conduct further research and evaluation of FIBL in different educational contexts and subject areas to refine and enhance its implementation for maximum student benefit. By undertaking studies spanning various settings, including different grade levels, socioeconomic backgrounds, and school types, researchers can assess the broad applicability of FIBL's effectiveness and pinpoint factors that may influence its outcomes. Furthermore, exploring FIBL's integration into various Science subjects beyond Biology, such as Chemistry, and Physics, can offer valuable insights into its adaptability and efficacy across the curriculum.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study had adhered to the ethical standards in research particularly during the data gathering procedure. Before gathering data, a letter of permission was addressed to the Central Mindanao Laboratory School Principal which was channeled through the chair of the Science Education Department. This ensured that proper authorization was obtained in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the school. Furthermore, informed consent which contains the objectives of the study, research intervention, potential risks, and benefits was also disseminated to all research participants. With this informed consent, the participants were fully aware of the purpose of the action research which is to primarily enhance their conceptual understanding on General Biology 2 through the use of Flipped Inquiry-Based Learning (FIBL). In terms of voluntary participation, the participants of the study have the right to withdraw from being the research participants without negative consequences. They were not also forced to answer the pretest, posttest, and the retention test which ensured that their involvement in the study was entirely voluntary. To remain anonymous and confidential, the students were represented by code numbers instead of their actual names during the data analysis to guarantee confidentiality of their personal information. Aside from this, the participants of the study were also protected from all sorts of harm. The researchers also ensured that this study has no conflict of interest, the references were properly cited, and the results provided were accurate and unbiased. Lastly, the contents of this study were original and free from plagiarism.

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